

Artificial Intelligence in Everyday Life

Educating the public through an open, distance-learning course

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ABSTRACT

With the rise of data-driven AI and its “democratization”, we are all interacting with AI-enabled technologies in everyday life. However, not everyone understands how these technologies work. There are many misconceptions surrounding what they can and cannot do, and what are the risks and benefits. Thus, there is a need to educate the general public about *everyday AI*, upscaling their algorithmic literacy and helping them become more informed, responsible users. We describe the development and evaluation of an eight-week course open to the public, *AI in Everyday Life*. Pre- and post-course questionnaires were used to evaluate the impact of the course and participants’ attitudes towards AI applications. The results suggest that more targeted educational approaches are needed for the general public to fully understand the strengths and weaknesses of the use of AI-enabled technologies.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Social and professional topics** → **Computing education**.

KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence, AI Education, AI literacy, distance learning

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1 INTRODUCTION

Today, we are in constant contact with “smart” technologies that seem to know a lot about us. We use narrow artificial intelligence (AI) applications daily, including assistants such as “Siri” or “Alexa” that help us make a phone call, or search engines that return the information we request in just a few seconds. However, there are many widespread misconceptions about AI [10]. What is it, and what is it not? If we are to have a healthy coexistence with AI, we need to think critically about this first, key question.

Several studies have considered the design and evaluation of curriculum and courses on Machine Learning (ML) and AI [12], targeting primarily university students in computer science (CS) [9, 29, 32], students in majors other than CS [33], younger students in middle-school, and K-12 students and teachers [13, 15, 17, 21].

Organizations such as the Association for the Advancement of Artificial Intelligence¹ (AAAI) are joining forces with teachers in K-12 education to understand how AI education at this level should be designed [31]. They provide tools and resources, as well as ideas and recommendations for curriculum design to help teachers incorporate AI education in their courses. Co-design workshops with K-12 teachers and researchers were used in [15], for identifying what needs to be included in an AI curriculum for K-12 education. Results were similar to other studies calling for more support for teachers and dedicated material for children in K-12. Sabuncuoglu [21], developed a 36-week, open-source AI curriculum for middle school education. The course was well received by students and teachers during the workshops, but the author noted the difficulties for teachers to keep up with this fast-changing technology and the need for directions on what should be taught. In a similar spirit, and acknowledging the need for preparing future generations to be informed citizens and critical consumers of AI technology, Lee et al. designed and implemented a workshop for developing the AI literacy of middle-school children. Pre- and post-workshop questionnaires showed that the students’ AI literacy improved and they were more aware of AI career opportunities [13].

For the successful implementation of AI education specifically designed to upskill and reskill the broad public, policymakers need to be driven by national strategies. In [24], a thematic analysis was applied to the policies documenting 24 national strategies for AI, demonstrating that education for AI is a common topic discussed by policymakers in different nations. Themes emerged around three main areas, *preparing the workforce for AI*, *training AI experts* and *public AI literacy*. In their majority, national policies emphasize that educating the public about AI, its risks and opportunities, will allow for more active participation in policy development, greater acceptance of AI and algorithms, and less obstruction to the development and dissemination of the technology, while preparing them to be more critical consumers of AI. There are countries that launched centrally coordinated educational programs designed for different groups, from K-12 to adults and AI experts. Singapore [27], Qatar [4], Finland and Sweden [7] are just a few. Elements of AI [7] is a course launched in Finland that has also been taught in Sweden since 2018. The main purpose of this course is to educate the general public on the basics of AI following the MOOC approach.

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¹<https://www.aaai.org/>

In addition to the design of courses and educational programs for engaging and upskilling the public, researchers and practitioners are employing AI technologies to provide a hands-on experience to learners. However, they either require that people have basic skills in using programming tools, upon which they can build with the newly acquired knowledge [19], or they are subject specific and cannot be used to teach introductory AI concepts [28]. Kasinidou et al. described a short seminar designed for CS students, focused on issues of Fairness, Accountability, Transparency and Ethics (FATE) in AI. At both levels, the seminar was integrated into the core course of the Software Engineering curriculum [9]. The authors highlighted the importance of educating CS students – who are not focused on ML or AI – on issues of FATE, given the increasing use of AI in software development. They studied how the students’ perceptions on these issues changed after attending the seminar, and called for more structured courses for both experts and young developers on these topics. In [29] a more structured approach was followed for developing AI and ML courses for undergraduate CS students and interdisciplinary graduate students in engineering. The authors provided further recommendations on designing and implementing such courses in various modes (e.g., on-site, hybrid and online). Wunderlich et al. [33] discussed the advantages of introducing ML to Business major students. Focusing on how ML is applied to real-world business problems, they argued that education on ML is necessary for the future workforce.

In [5], the authors conducted a series of interviews, in an attempt to understand what different groups of the community (e.g., the public, experts) would need in such courses. Their results show a clear need for developing and implementing separate courses that are specifically designed for various segments of the public. In this way, all citizens will learn about AI and the impact intelligent algorithms have on their lives, at a level that they can actually understand and relate to without necessarily having a technical background. Selwyn and Gallo Cordoba [25] conducted an Australian wide survey to examine the public’s perception and understanding of AI. Their findings informed the development of public education efforts to further enhance the understanding of everyday AI technologies.

In summary, several approaches have considered how to educate a range of audiences on AI, including both young people and adults who are non-experts on AI or ML. However, understanding what exactly is needed when designing AI education for the broad public is an important part of the process and at our best knowledge, there is still work to be done in the field. In this paper, we describe our experience and findings when developing, implementing and evaluating a course for raising the AI literacy of the Cyprus public. Specifically, we designed an open course for adults without a technical background. Cyprus has a unique profile as a small EU member state, which enjoys a high standard of living, and one of the highest rates of tertiary educational attainment in the EU.² However, when it comes to citizens’ digital skills, Cyprus is lagging behind; ranking in the last five in the 2021 Digital Economy and Society Index, with human capital (e.g., advanced digital skills, participation of women in ICT) being an ongoing concern. At the policy level, the National Strategy for AI³ has outlined the need

for educational initiatives for experts (i.e., cultivating AI talent) and upskilling the public (i.e., AI literacy) alike. Considering these, we undertook a first attempt at a large-scale course to examine the attitudes of participants towards *AI in Everyday Life*.

2 COURSE DESIGN

AI in Everyday Life was developed in the spirit of lifelong learning [11], which is fully embraced by the Open University of Cyprus. The intent was to offer a fully open course for up to 400 participants with no registration fees, as a service to the community. We offered a certificate of completion (CoF) to those who completed all required assessments but otherwise, participants were free to follow the course as they wished. Given the need to reach the public during the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, we opted for a fully online mode, supported by our university’s distance learning unit. We considered best practices for instructional design in e-learning (e.g., [8]) as well as the particular needs of adult learners [2], our target audience. We prioritized the principles described in Table 1.

2.1 Objectives

The learning objectives of the course were displayed prominently on the course website.⁴ The main learning objectives were as follows:

- Dispel common misconceptions surrounding AI, enabling participants to explain what AI is, and what it is not.
- Enable participants to recognize examples of narrow AI applications in their own lives.
- Analyze an application of AI, identifying its basic functions.
- Enable participants to become familiar with key AI technologies, including Computer Vision (and Face Recognition), Natural Language Processing (NLP), and Personalization, as to recognize these technologies in the applications they use.
- Understand and explain the key ethical and social issues that can arise from the use of AI applications.

2.2 Structure

The course was developed in Greek and consists of eight units – seven learning units and one interactive feedback session. Synchronous lectures – which were recorded and archived on the course’s website – took place once per week, beginning at 19.00 as to maximize participation. Students were able to attend the online lectures or watch the recorded lectures on their own time. After each lecture, a self-administered web-based quiz was made available. The multiple-choice type - quizzes, were designed to gauge knowledge of the key concepts of each unit, and provided feedback automatically to the learner once submitted. The quizzes were mandatory only for those who wanted to obtain a CoF. Nevertheless, all participants were encouraged to take all of the quizzes for self-assessment.

2.3 Learning Units

Introduction. The objectives of the first unit were threefold. First, participants had the opportunity to learn how a distance program works. The second goal was to acquaint them with the specific course. Finally, we explained the difference between narrow and general AI, and the fact that narrow AI is already a part of our lives.

²<https://op.europa.eu/webpub/eac/education-and-training-monitor-2020/countries/cyprus.html>

³https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/cyprus_ai_strategy.pdf

⁴<http://www.cycat.io/everydayai/>

Table 1: Principles of adult e-learning embraced by the team.

Principle	Best Practice(s)
Self-directed learning	Most adult learners are independent and self-directed, yet often have busy lives with many time constraints. To facilitate self-directed learning, we explain clearly the learning objectives of each unit, and provide all instructional materials ahead of time. A weekly quiz with automated feedback allows self-evaluation.
Multiple learning styles	Adult learners have varied backgrounds and experiences. To support multiple learning styles, we ensure that learners can set their own pace. We provide multiple educational resources (e.g., text, video, hands-on activities). Recorded lectures can be (re)reviewed at anytime, and asynchronous communication (e.g., the course forum) is encouraged.
Experiential learning	As adults bring a range of experiences to their learning, we provide opportunities to apply prior knowledge to their study of AI, as well as for reflection and assessment.

Analyzing AI applications. In the second unit, we examined the concept of *intelligence*, noting that with respect to machines, what is generally meant is that they are goal-oriented and able to engage in rational decision-making, within a very particular scope.

Computer Vision. In the third unit, participants were introduced to Computer Vision. Finally, we introduced AI bias and the potential for discrimination in computer vision systems.

Natural Language Processing. The fourth unit provided an overview of the key NLP applications, including speech recognition, text-to-speech, machine translation, and information retrieval, all of which are available on a modern smartphone.

Personalization. The fifth unit focused on how AI applications provide a personalized experience for users. Two types of personalization were discussed; 1) adaptable, and 2) adaptive systems.

Ethics. In the sixth unit, a working definition for *ethics* was first provided, and how ethical principles apply to AI applications was discussed. The notion of *Trustworthy AI* and the concept of human oversight of AI was also discussed.

Living with AI. The final unit considered the prospects and challenges of AI and strategies for a healthy symbiosis with AI.

3 METHODOLOGY

We collected data from two online questionnaires, completed voluntarily. Participants filled-in the first questionnaire before the first session, and the second one after the end of the course. More information about the demographics of the respondents can be found in Table 2. They were asked to self-report “Yes/No” as to whether they have taken “any training/course for developing their digital skills” and whether they have taken “any training/course on AI”. In both questionnaires, they were asked to respond to the following⁵:

- 1 Open Question: “How would you explain to a child (10-12 years old) what AI is?”.
- 14 statements reflecting their *attitudes towards AI*.
- 10 statements: “I would use an AI application for:” followed by specific systems where human (4 systems) or automation (6 systems) would ideally perform better.
- 10 statements: “AI systems are more capable than humans to perform:” followed by ten systems where either human (6 systems) or automation (4 systems) would ideally perform better.

⁵Statements were 5-point Likert scale and were adopted from [22] which is a validated measurement instrument that captures general attitudes towards AI [23]

In the post-course questionnaire, participants were asked to respond to six questions that aimed to capture the knowledge gained. They were asked to indicate whether they watched all lectures synchronously, most lectures synchronously, most lectures on their own time, or all lectures on their own time. Lastly, participants were asked to answer five questions designed to evaluate the course.

Participants’ free-text responses were coded and thematically analyzed [30]. Two researchers analyzed the free-text responses independently to define emerging categories. Multiple categories per answer were allowed and the co-occurrences of themes in responses were calculated in an attempt to capture the interplay of different themes. The categories identified by the two researchers were then compared, the disagreements discussed, and sometimes a dimension’s definition was amended to come to a final consensus.

4 RESULTS

4.1 What is Artificial Intelligence?

In participants’ attempts to explain AI, ten themes were discussed in the pre-course and nine themes were discussed in the post-course questionnaire (see Table 3). The most commonly discussed theme in the pre-course responses was **Like Humans** (48 of 117). The vast majority of the responses in the pre-course questionnaire defined AI as a system acting like and/or mimicking human behaviors. The main idea can be summarized by participant 13, “[AI is] the effort of intelligent people to make computers think and decide like people” (pre-course questionnaire participant 13 – pr13). The respondents mentioned that AI refers to systems and/or digital devices (e.g. computers, robots etc.) that can think like humans (pr1, pr30, pr66), act like humans (pr18, pr28), have human characteristics (pr26) and generally mimic humans and their behaviors (pr34, pr37, pr38, pr60). **Like Humans** theme was also popular in the post-course responses (15 of 56). Participants in the post-course questionnaire noted that “[AI is] a machine that will be able to reproduce human cognitive functions” (post-course questionnaire participant 35 – ps35).

Intelligent Machines was the most frequently discussed theme in the post-course responses (28 of 56). The majority defined AI as “intelligent machines that replace or assist humans in certain tasks” (ps7). Others noted that AI is computers that are thinking (ps11, ps14, ps31) or robots (ps26, ps45, ps51). Interestingly, **Intelligent Machines** was one of the least frequently discussed themes in the pre-course responses. Responses argued that AI is intelligent and

Table 2: Demographics.

	Pre-course	Post-course
Respondents	117	56
Gender		
Male / Female	36.8% / 63.2%	40.4% / 59.6%
Age		
18–24	3.3%	–
25–32	19.2%	14%
33–40	30.8%	26.3%
41–45	19.2%	21.1%
46–50	16.7%	17.5%
Over 50	10.8%	21.1%
Country		
Cyprus	37.6%	31.5%
Greece	58.1%	68.5%
Other countries	4.3%	–
Education level		
Completed High School	11.1%	5.4%
Bachelor degree	34.2%	41.1%
Master degree or PhD	54.7%	53.5%
Occupation		
Educators	27.4%	37.5%
Public Sector	17.9%	14.3%
Private Sector	12.8%	12.5%
Computing-related jobs	8.5%	10.7%
Other (e.g. accounting, health)	33.4%	25%
Had taken training about		
Digital skills / AI	65.8% / 23.1%	–

smart machines (pr104, pr105), which are able to think (pr95) and learn new things (pr102) without human intervention (pr9, pr35).

The second most commonly discussed theme in the pre-course was **Help Humans** (28 of 117). Most of the responses in this theme described AI as a computer or a device (pr12, pr56) that “*make [humans’] lives easier*” (pr34) by doing difficult tasks that are time-consuming for humans to do (pr13). **Help Humans** was also the third most common theme in the post-course. Respondents argued that “[AI] is the technology that protects us, makes our daily life easier, saves us time and improves as we use it” (ps55) and others noted that “[it is the] ability of some devices to perform complex tasks” (ps48).

The third most common theme in the pre-course was **Solve Problems** (21 of 117). Some respondents argued that AI solves problems that are difficult and require intelligence (pr15, pr57, pr61) while others noted that AI tries to solve daily problems (pr60, pr112). A few respondents mentioned that AI systems solve problems better and more accurately than humans (pr74). However, it was the least common theme in the post-course with only three responses.

Some respondents noted that AI is systems with the ability for **Decision Making** (16 of 117). Participants discussed that “AI is the execution of actions and decision-making [...] that do not require constant human involvement/intervention” (pr9). It is noteworthy to mention that this theme did not appear in the post-course responses.

Two themes received 15 responses, tying for the fifth most common theme in the pre-course responses: **Learn** and **Developed by Humans**, however, they received three and seven responses

accordingly in the post-course questionnaire. Most of the participants noted that “[AI is] the ability the machines have for learning” (pr63). Responses that opted in the Developed by Humans theme discussed that AI is made by other humans. Some mentioned that “[AI is] the effort of humans to exploit machines and/or computers in such a way as to facilitate their lives and daily life” (pr51).

Data is a notable theme with a total of 14 responses in the pre-course responses and seven in the post-course responses. The majority of the responses in the **Data** theme discussed that “*these machines collect information to work ‘smartly to humans’*” (pr8) and “[they] solve problems combining a variety of data” (pr15).

The remaining themes received just a few responses and only appeared in one of the two questionnaires. The least common theme in the pre-course responses, **Set of Rules** appeared only 11 times. Some responses noted that AI is algorithms (pr81) or algorithmic systems (pr7) that follow instructions/rules to make a decision (pr9) or do a task (pr108). Some post-course responses define AI as systems that **Follow Instructions** to achieve a specific goal.

22 responses in the pre-course responses and seven in the post-course fell under the catch-all **Other** category, which includes thoughtful responses that do not mention the other themes (such as “AI is the technology of the future” (pr107) or “[AI is a] mechanical manufacture that can perform some ‘mental tasks’” (pr97)) as well as responses where the participant indicated they “*did not know*” (pr54) or that they would use “*examples*” (ps49) or “*videos*” (ps3) to explain AI or that it was difficult to explain what AI is (pr73, ps33).

4.2 Attitudes Towards AI

Quantitative analysis was employed to explore whether participants’ opinions towards AI changed after they attended the course. To examine the differences between the responses in the pre- and post-course questionnaires, a non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test was used. Pre-course responses (mean rank = 80.01) were significantly lower for the statement “AI systems perpetuate social stereotypes and biases” compared to post-course responses (mean rank = 102.87), $U=2458.500$, $z=-2.913$, $p=0.004$. Although the results showed some differences between the responses in the other statements, there were no significant differences to report. Descriptive statistics have been used to discuss the rest of the results.

In the pre-course questionnaire, 83.7% selected the upper end of the scale (4-5) on the statement “I am interested to use AI systems in my everyday life”, while 3.5% selected the lower end of the scale (1-2). Interestingly in the post-course questionnaire, the positive attitude did not change (84.2%), but no one selected the lower end of the scale. In the statement “AI is used to spy on people” 53% selected the lower end of the scale (1-2) while only 20.6% selected the upper end (4-5). A substantial percentage of responses fell into the middle of the scale (26.5%). In the post-course questionnaire, opinions did not change much with 24.6% selecting the middle of the scale, 54.4% selected the lower-end and 21% selected the upper-end of the scale. The attendees agreed that “There are a lot of AI applications for good”, with 96.6% selecting options 4 and 5 in the pre-course, and 94.7% in the post-course, questionnaire. 87.2% believe that “AI can open new financial opportunities in their country” in the pre-course, and 82.4% in the post-course, questionnaire, showing that they appreciate the benefits that AI technologies may bring.

Table 3: Themes that emerged when participants tried to explain AI to a youngster

Category	Description	Pre-course	Post-course
Like Humans (LH)	<i>AI is systems that think and/or act like humans</i>	48	15
Helps Humans (HH)	<i>AI makes people's life easier doing difficult tasks</i>	28	12
Solve Problems (SP)	<i>AI is systems that are used for solving specific problems</i>	21	3
Decision Making (DM)	<i>AI is systems that make decisions</i>	16	–
Learn (LN)	<i>AI is systems that learn</i>	15	3
Developed by Humans (DH)	<i>AI is developed/programmed by humans</i>	15	7
Data (DT)	<i>AI is systems that collect, process and use big data</i>	14	7
Intelligent Machines (IM)	<i>AI is intelligent, autonomous machines and/or robots</i>	14	28
Set of Rules (SR)	<i>AI is systems that are consisted of a set of rules</i>	11	–
Follow Instructions (FI)	<i>AI is systems that follow instructions do specific tasks</i>	–	9
Other	<i>[falls outside of the established themes]</i>	21	7

42.8% noted that “Many jobs will be eliminated due to the use of AI” before taking the course, while a large percentage 41% selected the middle of the scale, possibly indicating that they were not sure. After the course ended, 49.1% selected the upper-end of the scale, 32.8% selected the lower-end and only 28.1% selected the middle option, showing that probably through the course they realized that while some jobs will be eliminated, others will be created. 80.4% “Would like to use AI in their work environment”, selecting the upper end of the scale in the pre-course questionnaire, while 6% selected the lower-end of the scale. In the follow-up questionnaire, 80.7% selected the upper end and no one selected the lower-end. The overall attitude was remaining negative before and after the course completion in the statement “I think that AI is dangerous” with 65.8% selecting the lower-end of the scale in the pre-course questionnaire and 57.9% in the post-course questionnaire. On the other hand, the attitudes were very positive on the statement “I am impressed by what AI can do” with 90.6% selecting the upper-end of the scale before they attended the course, and 89.5% in the follow-up. Similarly, they were positive in the statement “AI can have a positive impact on people’s welfare” with 88.1% being positive in the pre-course and 91.2% in the post-course questionnaire.

Participants seemed to be aware that “Some organizations are using AI in an unethical way” (57.2% pre-course and 64.9% post-course questionnaire). In the statement “AI systems can perform better than humans” 36.8% selected the upper-end of the scale, 44.4% the middle option and 18.8% selected the lower-end of the scale in the pre-course questionnaire. After the completion of the course, 35.1% remained positive on this statement, 29.9% selected the lower-end of the scale. The participants did not believe that “AI will take over control from humans” and selected the lower end of the scale in pre- and post- questionnaires (42.7%, 54.4% respectively). For the statement “I believe that AI systems are making a lot of errors” most participants selected the middle option, 47% in the pre-course questionnaire and 56.1% in the post-course questionnaire.

In the last two questions, it was interesting to understand whether participants can differentiate between tasks and activities that can best be performed by AI from those that need a human to get involved. We hypothesized that participants would state they would use an AI application for: i) tasks where human judgement is not needed and ii) those where AI systems tend to be more capable than (i.e., outperform) humans. A Wilcoxon Signed rank test was used to

determine whether there were any differences. Surprisingly, in both pre- and post- course questionnaires participants in the *I would use an AI application for:* rated the tasks where human judgement is needed significantly higher compared to those where technology would traditionally perform better ($z=-8.378$, $p<0.0005$), ($z=-5.843$, $p<0.0005$) respectively. In the statement *AI systems are more capable than humans to perform:* participants rated the tasks that human judgement is needed higher compared to those that technology would traditionally perform better for pre- and post- course questionnaires ($z=-4.627$, $p<0.005$), ($z=-3.817$, $p<0.0005$) respectively.

4.3 General Outcomes

Many respondents (36.8%) reported that they watched all lectures on their own time (asynchronously), while 17.5% indicated attending all lectures synchronously. 22.8% reported that they watched most lectures live and some asynchronously, while the rest reported watching most asynchronously and some synchronously. All participants selected the higher-end of the scale (4 out of 5) stating that the course is potentially useful for everyone. They also agreed that the structure was clear and effective and that the educational content was understandable and accessible. The vast majority (96%) agreed that the lesson met their expectations. 91% indicated that during the lectures plenty of examples and explanations were given.

After the course, respondents felt that they were able to better understand behaviors (96.7%) and analyze functions of “everyday” AI applications (86%). Respondents were also better able to recognize the use of AI in everyday contexts (93%). 91.2% reported that they understood the potential dangers of AI, while 89.4% stated that they were able to explain the ethical and social issues that can arise. Finally, 96.5% were able to understand the role of school and family in adapting the next generations to the 4th Industrial Revolution. 97 out of the 392 registered participants completed all the required quizzes and received CoF. The average score of the quizzes shows that learners were able to understand the topics (Table 4).

5 DISCUSSION

Our first goal was to implement and evaluate a large-scale course on Everyday AI, and secondly, to understand its impact on the attitudes of the public towards AI and its use. Our findings build on previous work [17] that reflects the need for educating individuals about AI, positioning them to be able to critically evaluate AI, and

Table 4: Number of views of each video-lecture, # responses to the unit quiz, mean score (out of 10) and the median.

Unit	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Views	225	120	93	69	56	41	44
Responses	-	155	150	127	142	120	115
Score(μ)	-	7.66	6.86	7.78	7.78	8.01	8.81
Median	-	8	7	8	9	8	9

use it productively. Previous work suggested that increasing public awareness about AI can be achieved through adult formal education where AI concepts can be understood without non-computer scientists being overwhelmed [18, 24]. Clearly, education has a great role to play in affecting people’s views on trusting algorithmic systems.

What is AI. Many participants thought of AI as machines that “think” like humans and/or have human characteristics. This finding aligns with [1], which found that half of their participants define AI as a computer that thinks or learns. The most common idea after completing the course was that AI is “intelligent machines” or “robots” that act smart and/or autonomous, although participants might not have a clear understanding of what made it intelligent. These findings also suggest that there is a tendency to think that AI is capable of approaching and/or exceeding human levels of intelligence [25]. It is well established that the public’s perception of AI is affected by media such as science fiction movies [3, 26], where technology is usually exaggerated in its actual capabilities.

It is reassuring that some participants recognized that AI is developed by humans to help in complex activities. In defining AI, some also mentioned that there are systems that Follow Instructions or a Set of Rules and collect and process Big Data. Interestingly, although some acknowledged that AI Solves Problems and Learns in pre-course questionnaire, very few mentioned these themes in the post-course responses. This suggests that even after attending a short course, participants were not able to fully understand AI systems. This was also evident in [34], which found that after attending a workshop on AI, students developed a complex understanding of AI. At the same time, we can see that public perception of AI can be influenced by learning experiences [20].

Attitudes Towards AI. The course raised awareness about social stereotypes and biases as participants indicated, which is one of the important aspects of introductory courses and awareness educational programs on AI. Participants appeared aware of the potential for AI to be used in an unethical way, however, they were fascinated by what AI can do. Similar to [34] participants joined the course with a positive attitude towards AI systems, which was not surprising given that this was a self-selected program, and their positive attitude remained even after the course completion. They did not seem to believe that AI systems are made for spying on people or are dangerous, but rather that AI applications can be utilized for benefiting societies, financially, socially and in welfare. It is evident that through the course participants realized that although many jobs will be eliminated others will be created, and they seem eager to use AI in their work environments. Perhaps one of the most interesting findings in this work is that participants seemed to be trusting AI algorithms for performing tasks where

human judgement is needed. Similar results were reported by Logg et al. [16] where participants in one of their experiments reported trust in the algorithms compared to human judgement when the opposite was expected. There is evidence [6] that humans tend to trust AI enabled technologies more as these are becoming “smarter” and more robust. Further investigation is needed for understanding this finding. These results can shed light on the complex task that we have in educating the general public and creating awareness of how AI enabled technologies affect everyday life.

Overall results, show that participants were able to understand the positives and negatives that AI can bring to their daily lives. Generally, they felt that they are able to understand the basic functions of AI, but also explain the ethical and social issues that may arise. These findings align with previous work [9, 14, 18], reporting that after short seminars/courses on FATE, participants felt more knowledgeable on related topics, reported significant changes in perceptions and attitudes towards FATE and an increase in conceptual understanding of AI and knowledge of potential bias.

Limitations. Although 117 of 392 registered participants completed the pre-course questionnaire, only 56 completed the post-course questionnaire and 97 received a CoF. We need to understand the reasons behind this dropout in a follow-up study and investigate motivational approaches for people to participate more actively. Second, participants of this study were interested in learning about AI and they understand the importance of being educated about such topics; hence, their responses should not be generalized to the entire population. Thus, further work is needed in order to gather the opinions of the broader public.

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The rise of AI has attracted a lot of attention in the research community, however, little research has been devoted to educating the general public about AI. In this paper, we describe the implementation and evaluation of an open, distance-learning course about AI. We examined how an eight-week-long course impacted the attitude of our participants toward AI technologies. Overall our results show that after completing the course our participants had a better understanding of AI and its positive and negative aspects. Nevertheless, our participants were aware of AI and had a positive attitude towards AI before attending the course, thus, their attitudes did not significantly change after the completion of the course.

We plan to continue offering this course through our university’s distance learning program and open it to the general public to investigate further their needs for developing their AI and algorithmic literacy, but also to evaluate the course on a larger scale and improve and enrich it accordingly. As a next step, we are planning to advertise it in more traditional outlets (beyond social media) in an attempt to reach people coming from different age groups and socio-economic backgrounds.

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